
Deliverable D3.8

Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu – v3

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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable is the third of a set of deliverables presenting the results of task “T3.3 - Definition and creation of a Governance structure and business model”. The deliverable provides an overview of the concrete steps conducted by the SWForum project to develop a long-lasting organization focusing on software engineering and acting as collector and amplifier of the ideas and initiatives emerging from the European software engineering community. Moreover, it presents the plan for the future steps aiming at consolidating the community and finalizing its structure and governance mechanisms (including decision mechanisms, conflict resolution, and membership types).</p> <p>This third release includes also the exploitation plan of SWForum.eu.</p>
Keyword List:	Fellowship programme, organization of the Forum, governance structure
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Terms and abbreviations

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SE	Software Engineering
SW	Software
SWForum.eu	European Forum of the Software research community

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Executive Summary

This is the third deliverable in the context of task T3.3 - Definition and creation of a governance structure and business model of the SWForum.eu project. The main objective of the task is to enable the development of a self-sustaining community that has the potential to continue its activity after the end of the SWForum.eu project. The activities within the task have concerned the following aspects: i) the analysis of the governance structures and business models adopted in existing communities with the objective of gathering information on reusable and potentially applicable best practices, ii) the definition of a fellowship programme aiming at aggregating around the community active experts, iii) the definition of an impact and exploitation plan for the project outcomes.

The current deliverable elaborates on the following pillars that we argue are the elements to nurture the community:

- ▣ A set of content-delivery assets that enable discussion and networking in the community.
- ▣ The organization of events of interest for the community.
- ▣ The development of contacts with other organizations to assess the possibility to join forces or support them with specific initiatives.

Moreover, it presents an analysis of the impact the SWForum.eu project is creating and the plan for further exploitation.

The presented analysis shows that, at the current stage and given the currently available communication tools, including those specifically developed as part of the project, the community does not require specific organizational and governance structure, as it tends to recompose around common interests in specific areas. This has been demonstrated by the fact that the community has well reacted to all our initiatives and its members have participated to the events that were considered most interesting for them.

1 Introduction

SWForum.eu aims to produce a self-sustainable forum with real time commitment of experts and young people both from academia and from the community of talented software developers. This deliverable aims to outline the steps toward this objective. One of the major challenges of the SWForum.eu project is to identify a clear scope for this forum that makes it distinct from the variety of organizations already in place and, at the same time, shows its added value for our stakeholders.

In general, the SWForum.eu project is developing several initiatives aiming at offering several services to its stakeholders. Among the others, we cite here the development of tools and methods to support the assessment of software projects and their market readiness, the definition of a research roadmap that aims at highlighting the current research directions in software technology and the possible gaps to be explored, and, finally, the organization of cross-fertilization workshops aiming at promoting the discussion and exchange of ideas on specific topics.

The focus of this deliverable is on the work developed as part of Task 3.3, which aimed at:

- ▣ Defining a governance structure and governance model for SWForum.eu beyond this project. These are the enablers of self-sustainability of SWForum.eu beyond the lifetime of this CSA. The proposed governance promotes the coordination of a working group composed of volunteer partners, opened to representatives from interested EU projects.
- ▣ Creating a Fellowship Programme aiming at involving experts in the software engineering and related areas supporting the SWForum.eu project in the creation of a long-lasting community.
- ▣ Defining a sustainability and exploitation plan for the assets resulting from SWForum.eu. This plan is based on the project results and timeline and on capturing key differentiators and how they relate to target audiences and potential revenue streams.

The work has started with the analysis of organizations focusing on specific research-oriented objectives to acquire an understanding of their decisional mechanisms and driving forces. This analysis has been reported in Deliverable D3.6 [1].

We then focused on the development of contacts with colleagues and other organizations with the purpose of identifying interesting common topics that could glue together a community of peers. This has been reported within Deliverable D3.7 [2].

In the last period, we have recognized that our self-sustaining community can be created around the following pillars:

- ▣ A set of content-delivery assets that enable discussion and networking in the community.
- ▣ The organization of events of interest for the community.
- ▣ The development of contacts with other organizations to assess the possibility to join forces or support them with specific initiatives.

Moreover, we have realized that, at the current stage and given the currently available communication tools, including those specifically developed as part of the project, the community does not require specific organizational and governance structure, as it tends to recombine around common interests in specific areas. Therefore, we have decided to keep the definition of the organizational and governance structure of multiple communities for a later step and we have decided to focus more on nurturing the community with new contents and ideas for discussions and networking meetings.

1.1 About this deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a summary of the work briefly introduced in the previous section and carried out in the last project period (M16-M33). This is the third release of the deliverable and relies on what is presented in Deliverable D3.6 [1] and Deliverable D3.7 [2].

1.2 Document structure

The document is organized as follows:

- ▣ Section 1 (the current section) introduces the scope and objectives.
- ▣ Section 2 presents the content-delivery assets, i.e., the SWForum.eu discussion forum and Fellowship programme progress.
- ▣ Section 3 develops on the organisation of events of interest.
- ▣ Section 4 elaborates on the contacts with other organisations.
- ▣ Section 5 assesses the achieved SwForum.eu impact in terms of performance KPIs and presents the project's exploitation plan.
- ▣ Section 6 draws conclusions.

2 Setup of content-delivery assets

SWForum.eu is aiming to strengthen the competitiveness of European software research and industry by facilitating a sustainable forum for researchers, developers, operators and policymakers, as well as providing space for engagement, contributing to the R&I Roadmaps, policies and assets.

In Section 2.1 we present the two specific assets that constitute the basis for the sustainable forum. They are the web-based framework, which includes a web portal, a blog, and an online forum.

Instead, in Section 2.2 we present the fellowship program that has been the central element for creating a community of individuals.

2.1 SWForum.eu platform

SWForum.eu is a platform [3] dedicated to software engineering research and collaboration. Its mission is to promote the exchange of knowledge, foster innovation, and shape the future of software engineering. By bringing together academia, industry, and research organisations, the SWForum.eu platform serves as a catalyst for advancements in software engineering practices. With a thriving community of nearly 3,000 SWForum members, the platform is aiming to unlock the power of information and knowledge sharing and to enable a ripple effect of knowledge and collaboration.

The SWForum.eu website is used not only as the central communication and dissemination channel of the project but also as a discussion forum and contributes to pointing stakeholders towards the SwForum.eu events and blog posts. Everyone could share opinions and news that could be published in the Online SW-Forum¹ (research, news, events, or relevant publications, for example) by signing up for a free SWForum.eu account² and having his/her say in shaping the future of software technology in Europe.

The SWForum.eu website homepage serves also as a *project hub*³, mainly providing free visibility for projects that register themselves and provide information about their goals and outcomes. Moreover, it is connected with the project radar⁴ that aims at classifying projects with respect to focuses and maturity levels.

2.2 Fellowship programme

The Fellowship Programme is the instrument through which SWForum.eu is engaging early career researchers. We use it as another lever for keeping the forum vital. The purpose is to involve experts in the SWForum.eu activities to create an attractive “pull” effect on potential participants in such activities and events and maintain a high level of excellence in the interactions within the Forum.

The programme has been supported by a small fund that we have been used to pay a symbolic stipend or refund travel expenses to the research fellows interested in participating in the Forum meetings and activities. Even if this does not constitute per se an incentive for experts to become fellows, it has been useful to attract their interest in the Forum activities. The reciprocal interest has been then nurtured by the discussions during the cross-fertilization workshops and within the online forum and we do hope this will result in a long-lasting relationship.

¹ <https://swforum.eu/online-sw-forum>

² <https://swforum.eu/join-swforum>

³ <https://www.swforum.eu/project-hub>

⁴ <https://radar.swforum.eu/radar>

The Fellowship Programme has been structured in two parts. The first part has been connected to the organization of our workshops and has resulted in issuing calls for contributions and invitations to known experts. The second part has concerned the engagement of experts that have been asked to prepare blog posts for our online forum. In the following, we describe in further details both initiatives.

2.2.1 Involvement of research fellows in the SwForum.eu workshops

We acknowledge 22 presentations by non-SwForum.eu fellows in our workshops, out of which 5 speakers were reimbursed for their trip to join the particular workshop. Further information about the SWForum.eu workshops is presented in Section 3.

2.2.2 Involvement of research fellows in the online forum

Figure 1. Fellowship programme open call banner

The involvement of research fellows in the online forum has been solicited through an open call published in June 2022 with deadline for submission by the end of July 2022.

Representatives from the following organisations were also encouraged to provide feedback and input on the online SWForum.eu conversation and discussions:

- ▣ Software technology and digital infrastructure communities
- ▣ EC-funded H2020 and Horizon Europe projects
- ▣ Policymakers and decision-makers
- ▣ Software Engineering Experts
- ▣ SMEs and Large industries

Applicants were expected to submit a brief Curriculum Vitae (one to two pages) describing their background and areas of interest and an example of writing on a technical subject.

Selected fellows were expected to author a total of 10 blog posts (at a rate of one blog post every two weeks) in their chosen areas of interest, paid upon delivery of each blog post at a rate of 4 hours per blog post at €30/hour.

Applications were evaluated by a steering committee composed of SWForum.eu members by 15 August 2022. The reference period of the proposed activity is September 2022 through March 2023.

The open call for the Fellowship Programme has been oriented towards European graduate students, researchers or practitioners in computer science, software engineering, or a related area. Funding opportunities have been offered for them to write on the online Forum about the most exciting issues facing the community today, on the following topics:

- ▣ Advanced Digital Skills
- ▣ AI Machine Learning

- 📁 Big Data and High-Performance Computing
- 📁 Computing Continuum
- 📁 Cyber-physical systems
- 📁 Cybersecurity
- 📁 Digital Infrastructure
- 📁 Ethical Computing
- 📁 Green Computing
- 📁 Open Source
- 📁 Software Development Lifecycle
- 📁 Software Operations
- 📁 Software Technology
- 📁 Standardisation

The call received nine applications, out of these the steering committee decided to recruit six from a variety of backgrounds and institutions (see here for a presentation of the experts <https://swforum.eu/fellowship-experts>). In addition to technical expertise in specific areas, the group of experts is also providing policy-related contributions. These target not only decision-makers with recommendations to inform and improve the elaboration of software-related policies and programmes, but also practitioners in the field, with analyses in order to help them understand and deal with the effects of these policies on their products, services, and competitive strategies.

The blog posts are available at the link: <https://swforum.eu/online-sw-forum>.

There are 71 blog posts already published, 6 more are ongoing, covering eight of the initially proposed topics of SwForum.eu interest:

- 📁 AI Machine Learning
- 📁 Big Data and High-Performance Computing
- 📁 Computing Continuum
- 📁 Cybersecurity
- 📁 Open Source
- 📁 Software Development Lifecycle
- 📁 Software Technology
- 📁 Standardisation

3 Organization of events of interest

From September 2022 on, the SWForum.eu project organized or co-organized four workshops. Moreover, it participated into a concertation meeting in Brussels where it has established contacts with other relevant CSAs and initiatives. In the following, these events are presented in chronological order.

3.1 WeGreen workshop (September 2022)

The first workshop was named *WeGreen – Engineering Green and Sustainable Software in the Computing Continuum*. It has been initially conceived to be organized as part of CAISE 2022 in June as an in-presence event (see Deliverable D3.7 [2]), but the limited number of submitted contributions forced us to postpone. It was decided that the rescheduled event would be co-locate with the GECON 2022 conference that held in Izola (Slovenia). Moreover, we ran it as a hybrid event as we realized that, at the time, there were not yet the conditions to run a fully in-presence event.

The presentations were four in total and the topics that were touched upon included:

- ▣ Evaluation of the environmental impact of ICT
- ▣ The measures of Green Transition and Digital Transformation
- ▣ Green Deal and Digital Transition
- ▣ Greening and saving energy on ICT level
- ▣ Sustainability-Aware Software Architecting for the Future Cloud
- ▣ Sources of data center energy estimates

The final discussion has highlighted the importance of the following themes:

- ▣ Greenhouse emissions and the ICT contribution
- ▣ Sustainable assessment of the footprint generated from software systems
- ▣ Standardisation of the evaluation methodologies for ICT environmental assessment
- ▣ Positive environmental impacts of the ICT space for business and society;
- ▣ Energy consumption measurement & benchmarking
- ▣ Algorithmic efficiency
- ▣ Energy saving applications
- ▣ Energy-aware management of data centres
- ▣ Energy-aware services of communications systems

3.2 Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability (December 2022)

The “*Open Source Workshops for Computing & Sustainability*” has been an initiative promoted by the European Commission and co-organized by SWForum. The event took place in Brussel on 2 December 2022 and was our first fully in-presence event. The event has been organized in multiple parallel sessions, the SwForum.eu partners have been rapporteurs in several important sessions, reporting on the discussions from the event and provided an overview of the main conclusions drawn. Besides, session S3.1 “Open standards and industrial use for Open Source: Leveraging the sustainability of Open-Source projects and increasing competition and interoperability between different steps in value-chains” was chaired by John Favaro, Communication Lead in TRUST-IT partner. SwForum.eu has released an official report for the EC about this event [4].

3.3 FastContinuum workshop (April 2023)

The *FastContinuum* workshop⁵ has been co-organized by partners from the SWForum.eu, AI-Sprint, and PIACERE projects and has been held as an in-presence workshop of the 14th ACM/SPEC International Conference on Performance Engineering (ICPE 2023). The event took place in Coimbra, Portugal on 16 April 2023.

The goal of the workshop has been to foster discussion and collaboration among researchers from cloud/edge/fog computing and performance analysis communities, to share the relevant topics and results of the current approaches proposed by industry and academia. FastContinuum solicited full papers as well as demo, short and vision papers including reports about research activities and new ideas.

The final program included 4 full paper presentations and 3 short ones (they have been all included in the proceedings of the ICPE conference), one keynote given by Samuel Kounev, a prominent researcher in the area of performance engineering, and a panel discussion. The keynote and the panel have been organized in cooperation with other parallel workshops running at the same conference, Load Testing and Benchmarking of Software Systems (LTB 2023) and 6th Workshop on Hot Topics in Cloud Computing Performance (HotCloudPerf 2023), respectively. They have, therefore, given us the opportunity to join different communities.

In general, the workshop has offered an interesting overview on the status of research and technology development in the computing continuum and has highlighted possible opportunities for the adoption of the serverless computing and FaaS paradigm in the computing continuum as well as opportunities and challenges concerning the role of AI in the continuum and the dangers of trusting it too much in an acritical way.

3.4 Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum workshop (May 2023)

The workshop “*Concertation and Consultation on Computing Continuum: From Cloud to Edge to IoT*”⁶ was held at the European Commission in Brussels on 10-11 May 2023. The meeting was a two-day physical event organised within the context of the European, Cloud, Edge, and IoT Continuum initiative by the Open Continuum project in close collaboration with the SWForum.eu and UNLOCK-CEI projects and guided by the EC DG CNECT E.2 and E.4 Units.

The event was a significant gathering for the European ICT community, fostering discussion and planning on the future of research and innovation directions. SwForum.eu participation was mainly focused on the opportunities for establishing contacts with other CSA projects, Open Continuum and UNLOCK-CEI that, together, manage the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative⁷.

The full agenda of the event is available on: <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/concertation-and-consultation-on-computing-continuum-from-cloud-to-edge-to-iot/>

The first day of the event was concertation oriented, featuring numerous presentations and networking opportunities. There was an opportunity for Juncal Alonso to present SwForum.eu, as her coordinator.

The invited Horizon Europe RIAs which started in 2023 had the opportunity to pitch their projects, while the more mature Horizon 2020 projects and the Horizon Europe projects started in 2022 have discussed their assets, and shared lessons learned and success stories. In fact, it was an important opportunity for the H2020 projects to further exploit and handover their

⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/fastcontinuum-2023/>

⁶ <https://www.swforum.eu/events/concertation-and-consultation-computing-continuum-cloud-edge-iot>

⁷ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

results to the new RIAs. CSAs such as EU-IoT, SWForum and HUB4CLOUD have also demonstrated the accomplishments of the projects they have supported. This was a great opportunity for networking.

These presentations facilitated knowledge exchange and set the stage for future collaborations. Additionally, the cooperation mechanisms of EUCloudEdgeIoT (called “Task Forces”) were also presented, where Catarina Pereira, Martel BV Senior Dissemination and Communication Specialist, highlighted the importance of participating at the Communications’ Task Force, co- led by Open Continuum.

Finally, the day ended with individual panels of three H2020 CSAs that nurtured the relevant communities before merging into the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative.

A section of the Panel “The Way Forward” was moderated by Juncal Alonso from Tecnalia, the SWForum.eu project coordinator, together with another representative of the partner TRUST-IT, John Favaro, SWForum.eu Communications Lead. This dedicated panel was titled: “Software models, tools and processes for the continuum”. Each of the panellists highlighted the need for new tools to confront the advances in software technology that are characterizing recent years, especially within the Continuum. In summary, the idea that “software engineering” has reached its final level of maturity is contradicted by the challenges being presented by the growth and complexity of the Continuum, and software engineering remains a fundamental pillar of technological process in Europe.

On the second day, the discussion was focused on acquiring inputs for the creation of the next Horizon Europe Work Programme (2025-2027). The project coordinator of SwForum.eu, Juncal Alonso, took part in the Research Roadmaps panel where SWForum.eu has presented its research roadmap. This was also done by other initiatives such as HiPEAC, NESSI, AIOTI, European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud, INSIDE, FIWARE foundation.

There was a useful discussion on future R&I priorities and plans, contributing to strategic R&I roadmaps. This was a good opportunity to advance the conversation on the future of Cloud, Edge, and IoT computing. It is clear that as the boundaries between these domains blur, an open and inclusive society leveraging these technologies is within reach.

SWForum.eu participation at the event brought us valuable insights and experience, which we could wrap-up as follows:

- ❑ We exchanged know-how with the major EU funded initiatives and projects on computing technologies.
- ❑ We promoted the SWForum.eu work within the broader European R&I context for further adoption, exploitation and impact of our project’s outcomes.
- ❑ We established contacts within the European Cloud, Edge and IoT community to identify common interests and foster synergies and collaborations.
- ❑ We learned about use cases across several industrial sectors where European organisations are playing a significant role.
- ❑ We were part of the discussions about future R&I priorities and plans.

3.5 The Way Forward: Future Challenges in Software Engineering workshop (June 2023)

The final SWForum.eu workshop “**The Way Forward: Future Challenges in Software Engineering**”⁸ has been organised as a highly interactive in-presence event that took place at Politecnico di Milano, Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria (DEIB), Milano, Italy on 27 June 2023.

To set up the program we discussed within the consortium about the topics that we considered the most challenging today and we decided to select the following broad themes: Software Engineering and AI, Software Engineering for Quantum Computing, Security in the Computing Continuum and Sustainable Software Engineering. AI, security and sustainability had been analysed in some of the previous workshops as well, while quantum computing was new to the consortium and we all agreed that we should have explored the interest of the community in this area as well.

We issued an open call to collect proposals for contributions in each of the identified areas. Since we wanted to promote exploratory discussions on novel areas, we decided to look for presentation proposals rather than papers, with the objective of creating a white paper and, possibly, a publication with the elaboration of the workshop discussions.

The full workshop program was organized in 14 talks given by external participants and a wrap-up presentation given by one of the SwForum members, David Wallom from the UOXF partner. The complete program is available on: <https://swforum.eu/agenda-swforumeu-way-forward-workshop-future-challenges-software-engineering>.

The workshop has seen the active participation of more than 45 people. The talks have been quite engaging and shed light on multiple issues and perspectives in the four areas of discussion. The speakers have agreed to work with us in the creation of the white paper detailing the outcomes of the workshop. We are convinced by both our own experience and the feedback received from speakers and delegates that the physical events, including the joint dinner for the speakers, have been beneficial for reinforcing the stakeholder engagement and the creation of new networks and initiatives.

⁸ <https://swforum.eu/events/wegreen-swforum-and-hub4cloud-workshop-engineering-green-and-sustainable-software-computing>

4 Contacts with other organizations

We have analyzed the needs of various software organizations in Europe that are not yet addressed by others, such as VERSEN (Netherlands), SISTEDES (Spain), TIVIA (Finland), FIWARE Innova iHub (Italy), AICA (Italy), and GFR-GPL (France).

We have set up possible collaborations with existing Open-Source initiatives with European players such as OW2, Eclipse, and Linux Foundation. Further on, we are planning to collaborate with some of them to gain access to their community and achieve greater efficiency. In particular, industry specific tracks (e.g., Linux Foundation Anuket) would be a good way to gain easy traction with industry players. We have defined a good set of Open-Source related activities aiming to retain the attention of developers.

The CSA with which we have joined activities, inside the initiative EUCloudEdgeIoT, has established a collaboration with Eclipse and OW2 so, we take advantage of this and collaborate also with them being part of Task Force, led by ECLIPSE Foundation.⁹

Other than that, SWForum.eu has established a contact with two CSAs : OpenContinuum and Unlock-CEI both under the European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum Initiative, CloudEdgeIoT.eu. In particular, we offered to help in CloudEdgeIoT.eu taskforces by proposing topics for discussion, participating in meetings and initiatives, disseminating events through our communication channels.

More specifically, within the second taskforce we expressed our interest in conducting the following activities that have emerged as relevant and useful within the self-sustainability workshop we ran in January 2022 and presented in [2]:

- ▣ Support the development of training for developing OS software;
- ▣ Support initiatives for creating a platform for Software Engineering experiments and for European Sovereignty in empirical software engineering;
- ▣ Assess the possibility to create a federation of national organizations focusing on research in software engineering;
- ▣ Support discussion on specific topics such as:
 - how to measure sustainability of software
 - secure software development (including secure development lifecycles, evaluation, compliance)
 - engineering software running on quantum computers

⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/cooperation-mechanisms/open-source-management-tf2/>

5 SwForum.eu impact and exploitation plan

5.1 SwForum.eu impact assessment

As discussed in D3.7, the SWForum.eu exploitation is strictly related to strengthening its impact on the community. More specifically, the impact of SWForum.eu is directly measurable by its success in facilitating the integration and interaction of communities.

For what concerns the actions undertaken by SWForum.eu about the organization of workshops and management of the SwForum.eu forum, relevant KPIs for impact measurement are: *Number of participants in the organized workshops, Number of workshops, and Number of contributions offered by external participants to the community.*

A summary of those KPIs is presented in Table 1.

KPI	Measures
Number of workshops	7 workshops (4 live + 3 online) organized directly by SwForum, some of them, in collaboration with other initiatives (OS workshops, EC)
Number of participants in the workshops	Tot. 448 1st Cross-fertilisation workshop: [86] 2nd Cross-fertilisation workshop: [29] WeGreen: [40] FASTContinuum: [40] The Way Forward: [45] Open Source workshops: [200] Concertation & consultation meeting: [44]
Number of contributions offered by external participants to the community (<i>Speakers, webinars participants, not part of our institutions – not belonging to the projects</i>)	78 blog posts written by 6 fellows contributing with 13 blog post each 40 speeches given by speakers not belonging to our project at the events we have organized WeGreen: 4 presentations FASTContinuum: 5 presentations Way Forward: 13 presentations Trustworthy software and open source: 9 presentations Our webinars: 9 speeches

Table 1 Summary of impact KPIs

As for the actions related to the creation of the project radar and mini sites, the KPIs are summarised in Table 2.

KPI	Measures
Number of contacts in the database (<i>registered to all our events, not including SwForum members</i>)	113 (total 1034)
Involved software-related domains and industries	<i>Software technologies, Digital infrastructure, Cybersecurity</i>

Table 2 KPIs related to the creation of the project radar and mini sites

Overall, the SwForum.eu impact achieved has the following coverage:

- ❑ Create a lasting legacy of the form of a profiled European Community database of ecosystem stakeholders engaged through SWForum.eu, e.g. subscribed members, participants of events & webinars (project and 3rd-party).
- ❑ Facilitate end-user adoption of the software project results through the creation of synergies and links to ecosystem players, e.g. cross-fertilization workshops, webinars, and 3rd-party events, with a strong focus on the uptake potential and exploitation of results.
- ❑ Provide new channels for industry engagement with the SW Forum in its development and sustainable form.
- ❑ Elevating software technology across the EU to assure broad coverage of EU priority topics and avoid the current defragmentation that exists. The Sustainability workshops were a direct initiative toward this impact.
- ❑ Promoting the growth of a densely connected ecosystem of communities across the EU. The facilities of the platform (such as the forum, hub, radar, MTRL measurements) are concrete initiatives in that direction.
- ❑ Strengthening of the Digital Single Market. The workshops that have been held so far are contributing significantly toward this impact. The goal to strengthen and hopefully federate the national software initiatives is having a direct impact on this.
- ❑ Raising awareness among the end user community. The platform facilities as well as the outreach events are equally valuable for the end user community as for the provider community.
- ❑ Contributing to capacity building in the software domain. This is a goal of the EU in the software area and has been identified in the sustainability workshop as a key issue. The online forum is already being used to publicize training and general capacity-building initiatives available in the software domains of interest. It is worth also noting that specific EU priorities such as cybersecurity awareness and capacity building as well as open source are being given particular attention in SWForum.eu.
- ❑ The SwForum.eu impact is coupled with measurable KPIs, covering both project outputs and increase of the policy effectiveness.

5.2 Exploitation of the concrete SWForum.eu assets

SWForum.eu endeavoured to take advantage of opportunities arising from the Covid-19 pandemic emergency by converting efforts originally planned for live event support to the development of sustainable alternative instruments that could feed into its portfolio of products and services. Given the strong and enduring diminution of live interactive activities over the course of the pandemic, we re-routed efforts to the improvement of the online discussion forum facility. Originally the forum facility was minimal in its features, intended only to support secondary interaction to live events. Over the course of the project, Trust-IT added new functionalities, ranging from voting (e.g., upvote, downvote) facilities to refined posting categories, to more robust and expressive blogging features, bringing it closer to the kind of facility expected from commercial forums such as LinkedIn.

The development of the facility received another impetus with the launch of the Fellowships Programme, which led to new requirements from the Fellows bloggers such as enrichment of the facilities to suppose better and more attractive graphical layouts that could appeal to the wider community of readers in software engineering. This development activity has resulted in the Trust-IT product “Forum+”, which is now part of the product portfolio.

A second line of exploitation is in fact the concept behind the Fellowships Programme. The Trust-IT product “Grants Facility” was customized to support the distribution of contracts for blog posting to individuals, and the resulting success of the Fellowships Programme will become a

model for further exploitation of the concept in other projects in order to ensure successful forum animation and community building (a pain point in many previous projects).

The impact of the Fellowships Programme has been considerable, with the effect of extending significantly the number of contributions offered by external participants to the SWForum.eu community. This was possible through the careful selection of applicants whose backgrounds and current occupational profiles were independent of and complementary to those of the consortium partners and the research projects associated with the SWForum.eu CSA. As a result, we received contributions that varied widely across the sector of software technologies, touching upon subjects that were not touched upon within the existing community of projects. For example, an entire series of posts on current and upcoming EU legislation pertinent to software technologies was curated by one of our Fellows – a topic that was not being directly addressed within the existing community. Other posts by Fellows treated topics ranging from advanced cybersecurity to technical debt in software development. All the Fellows were external to the SWForum.eu community of projects, enriching it with new, often orthogonal perspectives.

These activities have allowed to position SWForum.eu as a valid provider of information and support around software (and to some extent also hardware) open-source initiatives in Europe, and Trust-IT as well as PoliMi plan to exploit this newly-acquired validation in proposals for further open source-related activities.

Other than that, the exploitation plan of the project's assets developed by the University of Oxford is as follows:

- ❑ Both the MTRL (Market & Technology Readiness Level) Toolkit and Project Radar will be released as opensource generalised packages that can be reused but other projects. This will include basic guides on required customisation for both.
- ❑ They will communicate with AI and Quantum research communities in the UOXF to disseminate outcomes from SWForum.eu in these areas and engage them with communities mediated through SWForum.eu.
- ❑ Investigate MTRL usage outside of software and other IT areas to areas aligned with Oxford lead Prof Wallom's energy informatics area and more generally the energy domain which is the subject of a >£4m internal investment by the University of Oxford.

The exploitation plan of the other SWForum.eu asset, the Research Roadmaps [5], is spread around the following ideas:

TECNALIA's DIGITAL Division and the Software Key Emerging Technology (KET) Group will exploit the research and innovation roadmaps in software technologies, digital infrastructures and cybersecurity to align its strategy to the insights concluded in the roadmap. The results from the roadmaps and the research and innovation topics discussed will be especially relevant for the core groups of Cybersecurity, High Performance Architectures, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Technologies. After analysis and study of the potential of such topics in the context Tecnalía ecosystem, they could be incorporated to the strategic research lines of such groups and to the services and products portfolio of TECNALIA.

TECNALIA also plans to reuse the multi-factor and multi-scoring methodology implemented in the context of SWForum.eu to extend the roadmaps to other specific areas such as the Computing Continuum where similar roadmaps can be implemented following the same methodology.

Finally, TECNALIA will further engage with the already created community to continue working in the topic of Software Engineering and onboard them in on-going or future initiatives.

6 Conclusions

As discussed through this deliverable, the SWForum consortium has activated multiple initiatives to setup a community in the areas of software engineering for the computing continuum, in particular, including aspects related to Open Source software and security.

The pillars that have guided our efforts in the last period have been the following:

- ▣ A set of content-delivery assets that enable discussion and networking in the community. In this context, we have, in particular, created a software platform for discussion and networking and we have actuated the fellowship programme aiming at providing a small support to experts and researchers willing to participate in our activities.
- ▣ The organization of events of interest for the community. In total, as part of SWForum, we have organized or co-organized seven discussion workshops, five of which in presence the last 10 months. These events have shown a remarkable interest of the community around specific themes, notably, AI and software engineering, the management of the computing continuum, the business models behind Open Source software, security, quantum computing, sustainability.
- ▣ The development of contacts with other organizations to assess the possibility to join forces or support them with specific initiatives. We have entered in contact with several other initiatives and count to remain connected to them as individual SWForum partners to continue to be part of the community and help in its strengthening.

We have realized that, at the current stage and given the currently available communication tools, including those specifically developed as part of the project, the community does not require specific organizational and governance structure, as it tends to recompose around common interests in specific areas. This has been demonstrated by the fact that the community has well reacted to all our initiatives and its members have participated to the events that were considered most interesting for them.

Based on these considerations, we have decided to keep the definition of the organizational and governance structure of multiple communities for a later step beyond the life time of the project, we have focus more on nurturing the community with new contents and ideas for discussions and networking meetings, and we have established contacts with other running initiatives to be able to continue our SWForum.eu activities as part of them.

7 Bibliography

- [1] Elisabetta di Nitto, Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva, "Deliverable D3.6 Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v.1," 2022.
- [2] Elisabetta di Nitto, Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva, "Deliverable D3.7 Fellowship programme, governance structure and business model for SWForum.eu - v.2," 2022.
- [3] SWForum.eu, "Online forum," [Online]. Available: <https://www.swforum.eu/>.
- [4] SWForum Consortium, "Open Source Workshops for Computing and Sustainability," 2023.
- [5] J. Alonso, "D3.4 Software Forum Research Roadmap - v2," 2022.